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Exploring the Impact of Digital Divide on the Spread of Popular Culture in Nigerian Rural Communities

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to explore the impact of digital divide on popular culture in rural communities in Nigeria and its implications on sustainable development. The study is based on Marshall McLuhan's theory of global village which emphasised that the adoption of technological devices results in the expansion of cultural values and norms and the reconstruction of people's lifestyles and ideologies. An extensive review of relevant and related literature was carried out to determine the effect of digital divide in the spread of popular culture in Nigerian rural communities. Internet sources served as important tools for obtaining related documents on the subject matter. The study revealed that the lack of digital technology in rural communities in Nigeria has led to the restriction of global trends and exposure to contemporary cultural movements on digital platforms that serve as conduits for popular culture. The study also revealed that digital divide results in socio-economic and cultural isolation which limits the opportunities for Nigerian rural communities to participate in the evolving global popular culture. The study also showed that bridging the digital divide in Nigerian rural communities requires the concerted efforts of the government to make digital tools more accessible to the rural population, providing digital literacy programmes and designing online contents in local languages that can be easily understood by the rural populace. The study concludes that, by closing the digital divide in Nigerian rural communities, a more inclusive and interconnected society that will boost the economy of the rural communities will be created.

Keywords: Popular Culture, Digital Divide, ICT Tools, Rural Nigeria, Communities

Introduction

Nigeria, also known as the Federal Republic of Nigeria, is located on the western coast of Africa. Nigeria is a multi-ethnic and culturally diverse federation which consists of thirty-six autonomous states and a Federal Capital Territory (FCT) located in Abuja. It is the 7th most populous country in the world, with an estimated population of over 200 million (National Mactrotrends, 2023). Based on the density of the population in Nigeria and the provision of basic infrastructures, human settlement in Nigeria is categorised into two; these include the urban and rural settlements. There is no universal definition of what constitute an urban or rural settlement as diverse countries usually apply numerous criteria related to settlement size, population density and economic advancement to classify human settlements into rural or urban (Wineman and Andeson, 2020). Nevertheless, the rural communities in Nigeria serve as homes to about half of the country's population (World Bank, 2023). The rural communities are also associated with diverse indigenous culture and traditions. In addition, the rural sector in Nigeria is a major source of capital for the country because rural dwellers engage in agriculture. Regrettably, the rural sector is still largely characterised by inadequate basic infrastructure such as good roads, electricity, pipe borne water and poor access to information and communication technology (ICT) tools and other digital technologies which are the major driving forces for globalisation, better communication within and across nations as well as information and knowledge sharing. This is however in contrast to those who reside in urban areas who enjoy unlimited access to telecommunication facilities and other basic infrastructures. This uneven economic and social access to information and communication technology (ICT) tools and other digital technologies such as broadband, smart phones and the Internet is widely referred to as digital

divide. Digital divide is not only limited to the adequate access to ICT facilities but, in recent times, digital divide encompasses the reception and utilisation of digital tools, connectivity to the Internet, digital skills and literacy and the ability to transform the benefits of digital tools into social benefits that will improve the lives of individuals in a society (Ragnedda, 2019). Digital divide results in social inequalities in general which is strongly related to economic and social stratification. This has led to the marginalisation of individuals dwelling in rural communities politically, economically, and socially. Hence, digital divide is a socio-economic problem which has affected diverse individuals across different ages, classes, races and other social lines (Afolayan, 2018).

One of the effects of digital divide on the rural population in Nigeria is the limited spread of popular culture. Popular culture otherwise referred to as pop culture can be succinctly defined as a set of practices, beliefs and artistic outputs (popular arts) that predominate a given society at a particular period of time (Tavinor, 2011). It involves the aspects of social life that the individuals in a society are actively involved in at a specific period of time. Popular culture is usually determined by the interactions between diverse people either through the use of slang, food, styles of dressing, politics, education, greetings, music, arts, literature, fashion, technology and dance (Delaney, 2007). Popular culture is usually transmitted through the mass media which are typically categorised into four types: print media, outdoor media, broadcasting media and digital media or technology. The ubiquitous nature of ICTs and other allied digital technologies in recent times has led to the formation of online community or virtual world amongst heterogeneous individuals who exhibit a wide range of cultural characteristics (Ohiagu and Okorie, 2014). For instance, social media platforms such as *Facebook* and *X* (formerly known as *Twitter*) attract a wider population than other forms of mass media which makes it easier for people to interact and share information irrespective of their geographical locations across the globe in real time. The contents of digital media are also more visually appealing than other forms of mass media and always available every time the users request it. Digital media or technology also plays a colossal role in spreading different arts, cultures and heritages across every part of the world. Furthermore, the Internet which plays a central role in digital media has integrated all other forms of mass media as a result of its ability to disseminate information fast. For instance, people can watch television shows and listen to online radios on digital tools in real time. This practice is referred to as convergence of mass media (Chakaveh and Bogen, 2007). It is also interesting to note that the spread and penetration of popular culture through digital technology can be used to enhance education. For instance, the use of digital television clips, online movies, music and video games can be used to stimulate critical reflections and thinking, students' engagement, motivation as well as students' interest in the classroom. In addition, digital technology has been used as a tool to create awareness on health, injustice and other social and political issues that plague the society. The penetration of popular culture through digital media has therefore transformed the world into a global society. Nonetheless, the lack of digital technology in rural communities in Nigeria has restricted the opportunities for Nigerian rural communities to participate in evolving global popular culture. The rural areas are therefore usually cut off from the new social and cultural trends in the society. Bridging the digital divide that exists between the urban and the rural communities is therefore a sine qua non. It is therefore against this background that this study examines the implications of digital divide on popular culture in rural Nigeria and its implications on cultural identity, social cohesion and sustainable development.

Theoretical Framework

This study is centred on the Marshall McLuhan's theory of global village. The theory of global village was propounded by an American sociologist and economist named Marshall McLuhan in 1962. This theory emphasises that technological advancement marked by the emergence of electronic devices has made it easier for people to communicate effectively and to be more connected irrespective of their geographical locations, thereby turning the world into a global village (Truab and Hendricks, 2022). The theory also states that the growth and the use of technological devices result in the expansion of cultural values which ultimately changes a man's behaviour and in turn affect every facet of a man's social life (McLuhan, 1962; Jan et al., 2021). This change in culture as a result of the advancement in technology

results in the systematic reconstruction of people's lifestyles, ideologies, governance and institutional processes. The theory also emphasises that the advancement of digital tools for cultural transmission results in cultural erosion such as the loss of language, food, music, clothes and other social relations. In linking this theory to this study, it can be deduced that the emergence of the Internet and other digital devices has turned the society at large into a global village where the cultural values of diverse people are easily promoted or eroded.

Conceptual Clarifications

This section presents a review of the concepts related to this study. Rural communities in Nigeria, popular culture and digital divide are the concepts discussed in this section.

Rural Communities in Nigeria

The geography of Nigeria is shaped by the human settlement of the country. Human settlement can simply be defined as an organised group of human habitations in a specific location at a particular period of time. It also refers to the totality of a man's community which includes the social, material, organisational, spiritual and cultural resources that sustain it (Zivkovic, 2019). There are two major types of human settlements in Nigeria; these are the urban and rural settlements or communities. There is no universally acceptable definition of what constitute an urban or rural settlement because different countries apply numerous criteria such as settlement size, population density and economic advancement to classify human settlements into rural or urban (Ignatius and Madu, 2010; Wineman and Andeson, 2020). Nevertheless, Nigeria adopts the 20,000-threshold population as well as legal administrative criteria to classify urban communities (Ofem, 2012). This implies that a settlement is classified as rural if it consists of less than 20,000 people. Hence, all states and local government area headquarters are historically, legally and administratively regarded as urban centres (Avis, 2019). Communities are also classified as rural in Nigeria based on low level of infrastructural facilities such as poor road system, inadequate water supply and lack of electricity (Raji et al., 2017). Osunade (1981) also identified that the rural settlement in Nigeria is a community whose basic economic activity is agriculture which constitutes the bedrock of Nigeria's economic development. Emphatically, agriculture accounted for about 23% of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Nigeria in 2021 outperforming other sectors such as trade, telecommunications, manufacturing, oil and gas, real estate, finance and insurance (News Agency of Nigeria, 2022). Hence, the rural area is usually considered to be the bedrock of the nation's economic development. The rural areas are also known for the preservation of culture and tradition which are of great importance to the nation but which are at risk of being lost in the urban communities due to their heterogeneous nature. It is however disheartening that the rural sector which accounts for about 95% of the country's food supply has been persistently associated with low literacy, geographical restrictions, lack of access to digital technology devices, digital illiteracy and poor or no electric power supply. These factors contribute to the wide digital divide that exists between the urban and the rural population. The rural communities are thereby obviously marginalised in the aspect of popular culture showcasing modern politics, economics, education and contemporary social realities.

Popular Culture

In order to properly define the concept of popular culture, there is a need to define the terms *culture* and *popular*. Generally, culture is defined as the way of life of a group of people which includes their religions, mode of dressing, arts, beliefs, morals and values, languages, laws and symbols that are passed from one generation to another through imitation or communication (Itulua-Abumere, 2013). Hence, culture can be viewed as an umbrella term that encompasses the social behaviour and norms of a human society. There are two components of culture: non-material or symbolic culture and the material culture (Kaur and Kaur, 2016). The non-material culture includes the values, beliefs, symbols and the language that define a particular society at a particular period of time. The material culture on the other hand includes a society's physical objects or artifacts that are prevalent at a period of time such as means of transportation, buildings, cooking utensils, clothing as well as tools and technology. Culture is essentially used to express

the identity of a group of people and also to create a sense of belonging. The word *popular* connotes *to be liked or admired by a particular person or a group of people, to be common and generally accepted by the public*. Popular culture can therefore be viewed as a culture that is liked or admired by a group of people. It can therefore be literally said that popular culture is the culture of the people which prevails in a society at a period of time (Delaney, 2007).

There are however several authors that have defined the term *popular culture* formally. For instance, Mittell (2004) vividly defines popular culture as an expressive and shared system which is deployed for the production, transmission and consumption of simple but cohesive values that are readily accessible to and accepted by most members of a given society at any given time, simultaneously fulfilling both normative and practical social interests. Furthermore, Klaus and Funnel (2020) defines popular culture as an array of objects, practices, meanings and cultural contexts produced and consumed by mass audiences globally. Delaney (2007) also sees popular culture as products and forms of expression and identity that are frequently encountered or widely accepted, commonly liked or approved, and characteristic of a particular society at a given time. Popular culture such as entertainment, sports, news, politics, fashion and the use of slang is usually transmitted through a diverse array of mass media to a larger audience in the society. This practice encourages the adoption of certain trends in the society.

Digital Divide

Digital can be described as the system that generates and processes binary data. Computers are generally referred to as digital machines because they process information that has been encoded as binary values either as one (1) or zero (0). These values (0, 1) called the binary digits (bits) are the basic foundation for all computer systems. Hence, all computerised devices such as mobile phones, personal computers (PCs), smart television and smart wrist watches are tagged digital devices. In this global economy, the use of ICT facilities and digital technology is largely essential in all phases of human lives which include education, agriculture, health, entertainment, economic activities and tourism. The use of these tools provides quick ways for people to interact, seek help and gain access to better education, healthcare and improved business models. In spite of these advantages, there are a lot of obstacles that impede the access to digital devices. One of such factors is digital divide.

The term *digital divide* coined by Lloyd Morrisett is a term that is generally used to describe the gap between individuals, regions or demographics that have access to and use digital technology and other ICT related tools for a variety of activities and those who have limited or no access at all to digital technology. Digital divide typically exists between those in urban areas and those in rural areas, the educated and the illiterates, developed and undeveloped countries, males and females, physically challenged and those without any form of disability and the rich and the poor. It can therefore be deduced that digital divide creates a socio-economic imbalance between the people residing in a society. Mutula (2008) identifies four types of digital divide:

- a) **Social divide:** This can be referred to as the factors that contribute to digital divide as a result of social stratification. Typical examples include gender, race and ethnicity and class.
- b) **Economic divide:** This involves financial constraints that do not allow some communities to have access to and effectively use digital tools. These factors are usually related to poverty and monetary constraints which eventually lead to the lack of investment in ICT infrastructure.
- c) **Linguistic divide:** This occurs when certain communities are not familiar with the language and contents of a digital technology.
- d) **Content divide:** This occurs when the information provided by digital technology is not useful to a certain group of people in a community.

According to Ragnedda (2019), there are three different levels of digital divide: the first level, the second level and the third level. The first level of digital divide refers to those who are cut off from the use of digital devices; the second level of digital divide focuses on the lack of appropriate skills and knowledge required to use the digital tools while the third level of digital divide refers to the capability to transform the digital benefits, resulting from an effective use of digital devices into social benefits that will improve the lives of individuals in a society.

There are several factors that contribute to digital divide in Nigeria. These include geographical restrictions, high cost of digital hardware and software, epileptic power supply, poverty, lack of government policy, lack of skills and knowledge required to operate digital tools. Digital inequality has created significant distinctions among the urban and the rural communities, developed and undeveloped countries, the educated and the uneducated and also the male and the female gender in communities where gender digital divide occurs. For instance, the broad use of the Internet in urban communities enables the economy of a nation or community to be economically viable through online transactions such as e-commerce. In addition, the access to ICT tools has also been linked to excellent academic and scientific research. It has also been linked to the dramatic revolution of arts, fashion and music in the contemporary society. Furthermore, the access to the digital technology such as social media platforms enable individuals to build relationships and connect with friends and families easily. Nevertheless, the socio-economic gap created by the imbalanced access to ICT tools has continued to widen between the urban and rural areas in Nigeria.

Implications of Digital Divide on the Spread and Penetration of Popular Culture in Nigerian Rural Communities

It has been established that most rural communities in Nigeria are continually faced with the challenge of digital divide (Tech Herfrica, 2023). Hence, they are not able to follow the global trend and compete with their counterparts in urban areas and also globally. In addition, digital divide created as a result of the lack of digital tools in the rural communities in Nigeria has limited the spread of popular culture in these communities as discussed below:

- a) ***Digital divide stifles education in the rural communities in Nigeria:*** The advent of digital tools has transformed the mode of learning in Nigeria. Teaching and learning activities are not only confined to the four walls of the conventional classroom, paper-based textbooks, analogue blackboards, writing materials and notebooks. Students can now be educated at any location through online live or recorded sessions. For instance, the introduction of digital tools has also introduced virtual classrooms such as Google classroom which enables teachers and students to engage in teaching and learning processes irrespective of their geographical locations. Digital infrastructure such as interactive digital blackboard which has replaced the traditional black and white boards improves the motivation, engagement and the learning experiences of students by integrating rich teaching resources such as voices, texts and graphics. It also facilitates active and collaborative learning between teachers and learners. In addition, students can download vast number of documents on the Internet via digital libraries without having to visit a conventional library. Social media platforms such as *YouTube* and *Facebook* have also served as teaching and learning platforms for students (Vikash, 2013). In view of this, students in the rural areas who do not have access to digital tools are usually restricted from this popular culture and are not able to enjoy the benefits of digitised or electronic form of education. Consequently, the access to quality education in the rural areas is usually a challenge.
- b) ***Digital divide limits entertainment in the rural communities in Nigeria:*** Entertainment is a broad term that is used to describe any form of activity that catches the interest of an audience or gives them delight. Diverse forms of entertainment include music, dance, drama, storytelling, games amongst others. The ubiquitous nature of digital tools has also changed the face of entertainment in Nigeria. For instance, the genres of indigenous music in Nigeria are Apala, Fuji, Juju, Afrobeat and Igbo Highlife. These genres of music are usually played with traditional musical instruments such as *dundun*, *gudugudu*, *obo*, *lutes* and *kakaki*. Nevertheless, the advancement of technology in the 1950s brought about the use of gangan, electric guitar and accordion. Other forms of music such as highlife and jazz were introduced in this era. Music was also recorded on cassette, Compact Disks (CD) and tapes. The music industry was also dominated by the big record labels that controlled the music industry (Ofochebe, 2020). The delivery channels for music were through physical retailers, public performances, films and TV as well as analogue radio. Digital innovation has now changed the traditional model of physical distribution

of musical recording in CDs, tapes and other storage facilities to the use of Internet, social media platforms, streaming platforms, file sharing and peer to peer networks (Eemeli, 2023). This approach has revolutionised the way music is created, produced, marketed, distributed and consumed. The digitisation of music makes the copying of music easy and efficient. Music stored on digital devices also occupies less disk space than the conventional storage methods (Daisie Team, 2023). In addition, digital devices also have a great impact on Nigerian drama. For instance, the only means of distributing films was through the cinema, video home system (VHS), video compact disk (VCD) and digital video disk (DVD) (Adeseke et al., 2022). With the introduction of digital devices, films are now uploaded online with the use of the Internet to diverse video hosting sites such as *YouTube*, *Netflix* and *Prime video*. This practice enhances easy accessibility to films by the whole world. Nonetheless, those in the rural areas who do not have access to digital tools are usually restricted from this form of popular culture.

- c) ***Digital divide hinders effective communication in the rural areas:*** Digital devices have a big impact on the way people communicate with one another. Digital facilities such as social networking sites, video conferencing applications, instant messaging and electronic mail allow people to remain in contact, communicate and share information easily on a regular basis and in real time irrespective of the geographical locations of the users. Digital technology has also made communication fast, easier and cheaper when compared with traditional face-to-face communication and letter writing (Marwan, 2022). The proliferation of digital devices has made popular cultural contents more accessible in different environments. This has contributed to the awareness and greater knowledge of culture diversity across the globe. The occurrence of digital divide in the rural areas limits easy communication between individuals that are geographically separated.
- d) ***Digital Divide serves as an obstacle to social inclusion in the rural areas:*** Digital divide is the major challenge to social inclusion in rural communities in Nigeria. This prevents residents of these communities from effectively participating in social, economic and political activities in the country. For instance, the lack of digital infrastructure in the rural areas prevents the rural population from having adequate access to electronic banking services, electronic health systems and electronic government (e-government) facilities (Abdulrazaq, 2015; Adegoke et al., 2021).

Ways of Mitigating Digital Divide on the Spread of Popular Culture in Nigerian Rural Communities

The ability to access computers, internet and other digital devices has become increasingly important to completely immerse oneself in the economic, social and political aspect of the world. The inadequate accessibility to these devices usually results in the marginalisation of the rural communities from the current trends in the society. In order to facilitate digital inclusion in rural communities in Nigeria, the following strategies are hereby suggested:

- i. ***Provision of Constant Electricity:*** The Federal Government of Nigeria should ensure that regular and constant electricity is adequately supplied in rural areas. This is because the functionality of digital tools depends on constant supply of electricity.
- ii. ***Provision of Affordable Internet Services:*** The Federal Government of Nigeria should provide affordable and robust broadband internet service to all nooks and crannies of the society at large including the rural communities.
- iii. ***Increase in the Density of Telephone and Other Digital Devices:*** The Federal Government of Nigeria should also increase telephone density and the penetration of personal computers (PCs), mobile internet services and other digital devices in rural communities. This will increase the number of individuals who have access to digital devices in rural areas.
- iv. ***Reducing the Cost of Digital Devices:*** Digital devices such as smart phones and the Internet are usually very expensive and, as a result of this, most residents of the rural areas are not able to afford these devices. The government at all levels in Nigeria should therefore increase the

affordability of the Internet and other digital tools by subsidising the cost of these tools or by lowering their prices.

- v. **Design of Local Online Contents:** Usually, individuals residing in rural communities do not have the necessary prerequisite education to understand online contents. Hence, to close the digital divide that exists as a result of this, online contents that can be easily understood by the rural populace can be developed in local languages. This will encourage the rural communities to use digital devices. In addition, language barrier in digital devices can be mitigated through the use of natural language translation platforms.
- vi. **Awareness Programmes on the Importance of Digital Devices:** A proper awareness campaign can be done in the rural areas to educate the populace about the importance of divide devices on the spread of popular culture.
- vii. **Adequate Training on the Use of Digital Devices:** The government at all levels in Nigeria should provide adequate skills and training on digital literacy to rural dwellers. This will allow them to adequately operate and use the available digital devices.

Conclusion

Digital divide is significantly hindering the spread of popular culture in rural communities in Nigeria as popular culture is becoming increasingly digitised. Consequently, the rural population is often excluded from cultural innovations, shared cultural experiences, as well as national and global trends. Bridging the gap of digital divide in rural communities in Nigeria is therefore necessary to promote social inclusion and cultural exchange which will enable all Nigerians regardless of their settlements to contribute to and engage in the evolving popular culture.

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